

Current state of the art in therapeutic management of osteoarthritis

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Received 10 July 2025 ♦ Accepted 19 July 2025 ♦ Published 13 August 2025

Citation: Parvova I, Petkova V, Shumnalieva R (2025) Current state of the art in therapeutic management of osteoarthritis. *Pharmacia* 72: 1–8. <https://doi.org/10.3897/pharmacia.72.e164780>

Abstract

Osteoarthritis is the most frequent rheumatic disease affecting the joints. Recent advances in genetic and biochemical studies reveal the mechanisms behind the degenerative process in OA; however, there is no known compound that can definitively halt the degenerative cascade. Numerous pharmacologic *in vitro* and animal model studies have been conducted in recent years to assess the efficacy and safety of new chemical and biological agents and plant-derived substances—candidates for novel osteoarthritis drugs. The aim of the study is to present the current state of the art in the therapeutic management of osteoarthritis. Nevertheless, the primary targets of current treatment are pain relief and improvement of joint mobility. Autologous conditioned serum represents a new direction in the development of disease-modifying osteoarthritic drugs for the treatment of knee osteoarthritis. This therapy is a simple, safe, and conservative option with limited adverse effects and few contraindications. Biological approaches, such as the use of human granulocyte colony stimulating factor combined with autologous activated peripheral blood stem cells or platelet-rich plasma, appear to be among the most promising strategies for cartilage recovery. In advanced cases, for patients with osteoarthritis of the knee and hip, arthroplasty is performed.

Keywords

osteoarthritis, NSAIDs, hyaluronic acid, chondroitin sulfate, glucosamine sulfate, SYSADOAs

Introduction

Osteoarthritis (OA) is the most frequent rheumatic disease affecting the joints. It develops as a result of pathological processes of various etiologies and leads to damage of the articular structures. Recent advances in genetic and biochemical studies reveal the mechanisms behind the degenerative process in OA; there is no known compound so far that could definitely stop the degenerative cascade. Current treatment strategies in OA are based on symptomatic treatment, including a combination of different therapeutic options for pain relief and improvement of joint

function. The management of OA patients is complex and based on an individual plan for the use of non-pharmacological, pharmacological, and surgical treatment, aiming at reducing the pain and improving the function and quality of life (QoL) of the patients. Non-pharmacological methods include patient education regarding the nature of the disease, changes in lifestyle and diet, adherence to a diet, weight loss—for overweight or obese patients, especially for patients with knee OA—and managing comorbidities such as arterial hypertension, dyslipidemia, and diabetes mellitus. Systematic physical activity is essential—according to specific physical capabilities, patient

preferences, and the availability of trained staff to conduct aerobics, yoga, stretching, water aerobics, and others. Of great importance are the possibilities for physiotherapy, the use of transcutaneous electrical nerve stimulation (TENS), pulsed electromagnetic therapy, and thermal cures (Dougados and Hochberg 2019). In many cases, the use of an assistive device is required—a cane, crutches, walkers, appropriate shoes, and appropriate training for their use.

Pharmacological treatment

Non-steroidal anti-inflammatory drugs (NSAIDs) are widely recommended and prescribed to relieve pain in OA patients (Table 1). While measured to have a moderate effect on pain, NSAIDs have been associated with wide-ranging adverse events affecting the gastrointestinal, cardiovascular, and renal systems (Table 2). Gastrointestinal toxicity is found with all NSAIDs, which may be of particular concern when treating older patients, and gastric adverse events may be reduced by taking a concomitant gastroprotective agent, although intestinal adverse events are not ameliorated. Cardiovascular toxicity is associated with all NSAIDs to some extent, and the degree of risk appears to be pharmacotherapy-specific. An increased risk of acute myocardial infarction (MI) and heart failure is observed with all NSAIDs, while an elevated risk of hemorrhagic stroke appears to be restricted to the use of diclofenac and meloxicam. All NSAIDs have the potential to induce acute kidney injury, and OA patients with comorbidities including arterial hypertension, heart failure, and diabetes mellitus are at increased risk. OA is associated with excess mortality, which may be explained by reduced levels of physical activity owing to lower limb pain, the presence of comorbidities, and the adverse events of the used medications—especially NSAIDs (Cooper et al. 2019). Acetaminophen is the first-line oral treatment for mild to moderate pain relief at a maximum daily dose of 4 g and has demonstrated efficacy and safety with long-term use. However, it is known that at a higher daily dose of 3 g, the medicinal product inhibits cyclooxygenase-1 (COX-1) and cyclooxygenase-2 (COX-2) enzymes; therefore, the risk of adverse drug reactions such as bleeding from the upper gastrointestinal tract and hypertensive attack approaches that of the other NSAIDs.

The mechanism of action of NSAIDs involves reversible inhibition of cyclooxygenase (COX). An exception is acetylsalicylic acid, which irreversibly inhibits the enzyme; that is why it is mainly used as an antiplatelet agent and, additionally, as a weak pain reliever. The mechanism of action explains most of the therapeutic effects of NSAIDs, as well as their adverse drug reactions. Two isoforms of COX are known—constitutive form COX-1, which is found in platelets, gastric mucosa, and kidneys, and inductive form COX-2, which is expressed in inflamed tissues as a result of stimulation by cytokines. The latter is found to a lesser extent in healthy organs, e.g., kidneys. Drug development

of selective COX-2 inhibitors is aimed at reducing the impact on the gastric mucosa. Current recommendations include the use of COX-2 inhibitors in combination with proton pump inhibitors (PPIs) in patients at high risk of gastrointestinal bleeding and with concomitant antiplatelet therapy (Van Boxtel et al. 2001). There is a third distinct COX isozyme, COX-3, as well as two smaller COX-1-derived proteins (partial COX-1 or PCOX-1 proteins). COX-3 and one of the PCOX-1 proteins (PCOX-1a) are made from the COX-1 gene but retain intron 1 in their mRNAs. COX-3 and PCOX mRNAs are expressed in the canine cerebral cortex and in lesser amounts in other tissues analyzed. In humans, COX-3 mRNA is expressed as an approximately 5.2-kb transcript and is most abundant in the cerebral cortex and heart (Biswas et al. 2023).

Table 1. Types of NSAIDs based on their chemical composition.

Salicylates	Acetylsalicylic acid
Fenamates	Mefenamic acid
Propionic acid derivatives	Ibuprofen, Ketoprofen, Naproxen
Phenylacetic acid derivatives	Diclofenac, Aceclofenac
Indoloacetic acid derivatives	Indometacin, Sulindac, Etodolac
Pyrazolone derivatives	Methamizole
Derivatives of enolic acid	Piroxicam, Meloxicam
COX-2 inhibitors	Celecoxib, Etoricoxib
Anilines	Acetaminophen
Others	Nimesulide

NSAIDs have to be used in the lowest effective dose and for a short time or only when needed because of a number of possible adverse events. Han MH et al. conducted a retrospective cohort study to assess the gastrointestinal risk of non-steroidal anti-inflammatory drugs and gastro-protective agents used in the treatment of osteoarthritis in elderly patients. The study shows that the use of a COX-2-selective NSAID was associated with a lower risk of gastrointestinal adverse events than the use of non-selective NSAIDs (ns-NSAIDs) as monotherapy. Furthermore, COX-2-selective NSAIDs have a better safety profile than ns-NSAIDs in combination with gastro-protective agents (GPAs) (Han et al. 2019).

A comparative study of the efficacy of Naxozol compared to celecoxib with respect to gastrointestinal tract protection and pain relief in OA patients was conducted by Park MS et al. Naxozol is a new combination formulation designed to provide sequential delivery of a non-enteric-coated, immediate-release esomeprazole strontium tetrahydrate 20 mg mantle followed by an enteric-coated naproxen 500 mg core. It was shown that Naxozol is not inferior to celecoxib in protecting the gastrointestinal tract and providing pain relief in patients with osteoarthritis (Park et al. 2020).

The use of NSAIDs is associated with an increased risk of thrombosis due to inhibition of prostacyclin synthesis.

Arachidonic acid is a consequence of the breakdown of membrane phospholipids by the action of phospholipases A2 (Fig. 1). Cyclooxygenases (COX) are the

Figure 1. Prostaglandin biosynthesis pathways.

rate-limiting steps in the biosynthesis of prostaglandins (PGs). COX-1 and COX-2 convert arachidonic acid to PGH₂, with further conversion to specific PGs depending on the specific PG synthases. Prostaglandin dehydrogenase (PGDH) metabolizes bioactive PGs into inactive keto-metabolites.

In a systematic review and meta-analysis, Cheng et al. assessed the cardiovascular safety of celecoxib compared to non-selective non-steroidal anti-inflammatory drugs or placebo. The cardiovascular mortality rate of celecoxib was found to be lower than that of non-selective non-steroidal anti-inflammatory drugs (risk ratio: 0.75, 95% confidence interval: 0.57–0.99). There was no significant difference between celecoxib and non-selective non-steroidal anti-inflammatory drugs or placebo in the risk of other cardiovascular events (Smith and Cooper-DeHoff 2019). The U.S. Food and Drug Administration (FDA) approved Consensi (amlodipine besylate and celecoxib), a combination of an antihypertensive calcium channel blocker and an NSAID, for the treatment of hypertension and OA in 2018 (Cheng et al. 2021).

In 2019, Barcella et al. published data from a nationwide study in OA patients to assess the differences in cardiovascular safety associated with NSAID therapy. They found significant differences in cardiovascular risk among NSAIDs. Naproxen and ibuprofen appeared to be safer compared to celecoxib, including when the authors examined equivalent low doses. In terms of cardiovascular safety, naproxen and ibuprofen, at the lowest effective doses, may be the preferred first choices among patients with OA needing pain relief (Barcella et al. 2019).

NSAIDs may cause functional renal impairment in patients with preexisting glomerular disease (e.g., lupus nephritis) or other conditions in which renal blood flow is dependent on the synthesis of vasodilator prostaglandins. The use of NSAIDs can lead to acute interstitial nephritis due to idiosyncrasy. Hypersensitivity in the form of rash,

urticaria, or bronchospasm is characteristic of about 15% of patients. Non-immune mechanisms are believed to underlie this hypersensitivity. Although rare, anaphylaxis may occur. Another observed adverse drug reaction with the use of NSAIDs is toxic hepatitis. The mechanism of its occurrence is related to the accumulation of reactive carboxylglucuronidated metabolite.

Most NSAIDs are metabolized by CYP2C9—one of the isoenzymes of the cytochrome P450 (CYP450) system. For this reason, their simultaneous use with drugs such as amiodarone, fluconazole, fluoxetine, fluvoxamine, lansoprazole, ticlopidine, and sulfamethoxazole—enzyme inhibitors—leads to increased plasma levels of the corresponding NSAID. Conversely, drugs such as barbiturates and rifampicin—enzyme inducers—lower the concentrations of NSAIDs, and, as a result, a smaller therapeutic effect could be expected. Celecoxib is a known inhibitor of the CYP2D6 enzyme, which metabolizes substrates such as codeine and other opioid analgesics, metoprolol, nortriptyline, pravastatin, and propafenone. By blocking the biosynthesis of prostaglandins, NSAIDs also interact non-specifically with antihypertensive drugs, thereby reducing their effect. The prostaglandins mentioned above have a natriuretic effect. Water and sodium retention are observed during NSAID treatment, and these medicines act as diuretic antagonists.

Table 2. Adverse events of NSAIDs by system-organ class.

Gastrointestinal disorders	Bleeding, ulcer
Cardiac disorders	Acute myocardial infarction, acute heart failure
Renal and urinary disorders	Acute interstitial nephritis, acute/chronic renal failure
Hepatobiliar disorders	Toxic hepatitis
Immune system disorders	Rash, urticaria or bronchospasm, anaphylaxis
Vascular disorders	Thrombosis, hemorrhagic stroke

Opioids

Tramadol, buprenorphine, and other opioids are used for moderate and acute pain in short courses due to possible side effects such as nausea, drowsiness, dizziness, and constipation, especially in older patients (Fig. 2).

Wei J et al. examined the association of tramadol with the risk of myocardial infarction (MI) among patients with OA. In their population-based cohort of patients with OA, the six-month risk of MI among initiators of tramadol was higher than that of naproxen, but comparable to—if not lower than—those of diclofenac or codeine (Wei et al. 2019).

Figure 2. Therapeutic steps for the treatment of chronic pain.

Topical treatment

Topical formulations containing capsaicin and NSAIDs are widely used in OA patients. Capsaicin-containing medicinal products have shown efficacy and safety in clinical trials in patients with hand and knee OA. Topical NSAIDs may be considered safe in the management of OA, especially with regard to low gastrointestinal toxicity (Persson et al. 2019).

Symptomatic slow-acting drugs for OA (SYSADOA)

Combined glucosamine hydrochloride plus chondroitin sulfate (GH+CS) is commonly used for joint pain and has no known adverse effects. Evidence from *in vitro*, animal, and human studies suggests that GH+CS have anti-inflammatory activity, among other mechanisms of action. The results of a study demonstrate that GH+CS reduce circulating IL-6, an inflammatory cytokine, but are otherwise comparable to celecoxib with regard to effects on other circulating protein biomarkers (Navarro et al. 2020). Another study demonstrates that the combination of GS with conventional treatment seems to be more effective in improving pain and function than conventional hand OA treatment alone (Tenti et al. 2020). Diacerein has shown efficacy in clinical trials in patients with hip OA. The most

significant dose-dependent adverse drug reaction of the product is the occurrence of diarrhea.

Bruyere et al. conducted a long-term follow-up retrospective study of the incidence of total knee replacement in patients with knee OA formerly receiving treatment with GS or placebo. The study revealed that treatment of knee OA with GS for at least 12 months and up to 3 years could prevent total joint replacement in an average follow-up of 5 years after drug discontinuation (Bruyere et al. 2008). Medicinal products containing avocado/soybean unsaponifiables (ASU) are used in knee and hip OA, and their effect is less compared to other representatives of this medicinal class. Cho et al. provided a retrospective study to assess whether adjuvant Chinese herbal medicine (CHM) treatment is associated with the risk of joint replacement in OA patients. They used a population-based National Health Insurance (NHI) database from 2000 to 2012 in Taiwan. This study suggested that adjuvant CHM might be associated with a lower rate of joint replacement in OA patients (Cho et al. 2021).

Intra-articular therapy

An increasing number of studies are being published suggesting that intra-articular injections may be as effective, or even more effective, than NSAIDs and result in fewer systemic adverse events. The most commonly used preparations are hyaluronic acid (HA), glucocorticosteroids (GS), and, more recently, platelet-rich plasma (PRP) (Nowaczyk et al. 2022). For the treatment of early OA, the development of a disease-modifying osteoarthritis drug (DMOAD) for intra-articular (IA) injection—which is attracting attention as a point-of-care therapy—is desired (Toyoda et al. 2021). Abdelsabor Sabaah et al. conducted a study to compare the effectiveness of PRP versus hyaluronic acid (HA) injection versus corticosteroids in thumb carpometacarpal (CMC) joint osteoarthritis, based on clinical and functional outcome measures. They concluded that the three types of injection (PRP, HA, and steroids) produced good results in thumb base OA with regard to improving pain and hand function, but only HA had a long-lasting effect and the best results for both pain and function. The limitation of the study is the short follow-up period, which does not allow evaluation of the long-term effects of intra-articular HA (Vitali et al. 2020). Autologous conditioned serum (ACS) represents a new direction in disease-modifying osteoarthritic drugs (DMOADs) for the treatment of knee OA. This therapy is a simple, safe, and conservative option for knee OA, with limited adverse effects and few contraindications. It targets the main cytokine responsible for the inflammatory-degenerative cascade involved in OA, IL-1 (Abdelsabor Sabaah et al. 2020).

There is a significant increase in both fundamental and clinical studies evaluating drug delivery systems (DDS) for osteoarthritis in recent years. Steroid-encapsulating polymeric microparticles for longer-lasting pain relief are approved for clinical use. Electrically charged biomaterials for intra-cartilage targeting have shown promising

disease-modifying responses in preclinical models. Clinical trials evaluating the safety of viral vectors are ongoing, thus paving the way for gene therapy as an OA treatment (Mehta et al. 2021). Nano-/microparticles and/or hydrogels can now be engineered to improve the administration and IA delivery of specific drugs, targeting molecular pathways and pathogenic mechanisms involved in OA progression and remission. Gambaro et al. found that polymeric nanoparticles loaded with anti-inflammatory drugs (i.e., dexamethasone or celecoxib) are the most frequently investigated drug delivery systems, followed by microparticles and hydrogels (Gambaro et al. 2021).

Moretti et al. presented an overview of the biological and clinical role of clodronic acid in OA. Patients with knee OA treated with IA clodronate experienced improvements in pain and joint mobility (Moretti et al. 2021). Zhang et al. demonstrated that intra-articular HA injection is safe and improves pain in patients with glenohumeral OA (Zhang et al. 2019).

Younger et al. show in a study the promise of viscosupplementation with non-animal hyaluronic acid (NASHA)—a cross-linked hyaluronic acid product that has a prolonged intra-articular residence time—in the treatment of ankle OA. A single injection is associated with clinically meaningful reductions in pain and disability during a 26-week period and, in general, is well tolerated (Younger et al. 2019). Since local inflammation is recognized as contributing to osteoarthritic complaints, the Hand Osteoarthritis Prednisolone Efficacy (HOPE) study aimed to investigate the efficacy and safety of short-term prednisolone in patients with painful hand OA and synovial inflammation. The study shows that treatment with 10 mg prednisolone for 6 weeks is efficacious and safe for patients with painful hand OA and signs of inflammation. The results of this study provide clinicians with a new short-term treatment option for patients with hand OA who report a flare-up of their disease (Kroon et al. 2019). Hydroxychloroquine is a pharmacological alternative in patients with hand OA in cases of intensive joint pain and swelling.

Advanced therapy

Advanced therapy medicinal products are medicines for human use that are based on genes, tissues, or cells. There are three main types of advanced therapy: medicines based on tissue engineering, gene therapy medicines, and somatic cell therapy medicines. This class of products represents a new alternative for the treatment of a number of oncological diseases, muscular dystrophy, Alzheimer's disease, plastic surgery (injuries and loss of skin due to burns), OA, and other rheumatic diseases. Ex vivo-grown autologous cartilage cells expressing specific marker proteins, administered intra-articularly, are used for the treatment and repair of cartilage defects and cartilage lesions. There are ongoing attempts to create cellular constructs or tissues obtained by substantial manipulation to achieve biological, physiological, or structural properties in order

to regenerate, repair, or replace human tissue. The development of this area of science is a matter of the future, especially in cartilage recovery (Parvova et al. 2022). Papadopoulos et al. propose that their novel intra-articular administration of human granulocyte colony stimulating factor (IA-hG-CSF), combined with autologous activated peripheral blood stem cells (AAPBSC), is safe and offers treatment advantages not seen with other cellular interventions in early osteoarthritis (Apostu et al. 2021).

Other pharmacological options

There are several systemically administered pharmacological agents shown to improve the anabolic response in the case of cartilage lesions. Alendronate, glucosamine, chondroitin sulfate, hyaluronic acid, collagen hydrolysate, vitamin C, vitamin D, acetylsalicylic acid, and strontium ranelate have shown positive results in clinical trials. On the other hand, calcitonin, risedronate, doxycycline, and celecoxib did not slow the progression of cartilage lesions in clinical trials. Other systemic drugs or supplements—such as teriparatide, leptin, zoledronic acid, bevacizumab, atorvastatin, omega-3 fatty acid, naringin, selenium, zinc, magnesium, resveratrol, donepezil, naproxen, etodolac, ursodeoxycholic acid (UDCA), lithium chloride, and remapipide—show positive results in *in vitro* and animal studies, but clinical trials confirming the positive impact on cartilage repair are lacking (Papadopoulos et al. 2021).

Tetracyclines have the potential to benefit OA patients via multiple mechanisms. Further study is warranted to examine the optimal dose and timing of tetracycline treatment in osteoarthritis (Platt et al. 2021). Monoclonal nerve growth factor (NGF) antibodies are new drugs with the potential to provide pain relief and functional improvement in OA (Cao et al. 2020a). Lutikizumab is a novel anti-IL-1 α/β dual variable domain immunoglobulin that can simultaneously bind and inhibit IL-1 α and IL-1 β to relieve pain and dysfunction symptoms (Cao et al. 2020b).

Krocina TM, a herbal medicine made from crocin—an ingredient of saffron—has shown immunoregulatory effects in patients with OA, ameliorating the disease in a clinical study (Poursamimi et al. 2021). Flavocoxid is a prescription medical food used to manage OA symptoms. Safety concerns based on case reports raised an association with acute liver injury and hypersensitivity pneumonitis. Curtis et al. determined incidence rates (IR) of these safety events in a cohort of new users of flavocoxid and prescription NSAIDs. They found that the rate of hypersensitivity pneumonitis and liver injury associated with flavocoxid was low and minimally elevated compared to NSAIDs. Flavocoxid users had a significantly lower risk for hospitalized gastrointestinal bleeding (Curtis et al. 2020). Several randomized, placebo-controlled, double-blind studies—as monotherapy or combination therapy—have demonstrated the treatment efficacy and excellent tolerability of rose hip. The entirety of several compounds, including phenolics, terpenoids,

galactolipids, carotenoids, fruit acids, and fatty oils, can be considered responsible for the observed pharmacological and clinical effects (Gruenwald et al. 2019). Oxaceprol, a derivative of L-proline, is an established drug for managing OA with a better safety profile than NSAIDs (Durg et al. 2019). The Pycnogenol® patch (a thin polycarbonate patch) was effective in controlling mild to moderate pain, inflammation, and related symptoms in subjects with knee OA over a period of three weeks (Feragalli et al. 2019).

Surgery

Surgery becomes an alternative when conservative treatment fails in patients with OA, and knee and hip arthroplasty are the most frequently performed procedures.

Discussion and conclusion

Over the past five years, numerous pharmacologic *in vitro* and animal model studies have been conducted to discover new pharmacological options for the treatment of OA. A number of molecules not currently available on the market have shown promising results in cartilage healing, such as licofelone, sclerostin, cyclopamine, cyclodextrin polysulfate, AG-041R, osteoprotegerin, rhMK, beta-cryptoxanthine, NF-kappa β essential modulator binding domain (NBD), TGF-beta-neutralizing antibody, osteogenic protein-1 (BMP-7), fibroblast growth factor 2 (FGF2), and RhBMP-2. Perhaps one of these new molecules will establish a new era in the treatment of OA patients—to stop the degenerative process and to heal the joint cartilage. The introduction of anti-inflammatory molecules has been shown to reduce inflammation and thus relieve pain in OA, although some cytotoxicity has been demonstrated, especially for NSAIDs. Other molecules, such as antioxidants or disease-modifying osteoarthritis drugs, have been reported to improve the action of viscosupplementation. Drug delivery systems combined with hyaluronic acid could enhance the activity of the encapsulated molecules

and provide better control over drug release. Finally, biological approaches, such as the use of stem cells or platelet-rich plasma, seem to be the most promising strategies for cartilage recovery (Pontes-Quero et al. 2021).

Additional information

Conflict of interest

The authors have declared that no competing interests exist.

Ethical statements

The authors declared that no clinical trials were used in the present study.

The authors declared that no experiments on humans or human tissues were performed for the present study.

The authors declared that no informed consent was obtained from the humans, donors or donors' representatives participating in the study.

The authors declared that no experiments on animals were performed for the present study.

The authors declared that no commercially available immortalised human and animal cell lines were used in the present study.

Use of AI

No use of AI was reported.

Funding

No funding was reported.

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Data availability

All of the data that support the findings of this study are available in the main text.

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